

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

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Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

The time-optimal problem of steering two rigidly connected objects between prescribed states

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Abstract In this paper, the problem of optimal control of two rigidly connected objects moving in the plane is investigated. The problem is interpreted the synthesis of a minimum-time optimal control is carried out using Pontryagin's maximum principle. The structure of the controls, switching functions, and the geometric interpretation of the optimal trajectory are analyzed in detail. The developed control concepts are of significant importance for applications to motion planning problems of unmanned aerial vehicles.

Keywords: optimal control, Pontryagin's maximum principle, minimum time, switching functions.

1. Introduction

Optimal control theory studies the problems of controlling dynamical systems in the most efficient manner according to a given criterion and serves as an important theoretical foundation for the analysis of complex technical and engineering systems [6], [17]. The fundamental achievements of this theory are associated with the maximum principle developed by L. S. Pontryagin [16] and his scientific school, which is widely used in solving minimum-time and minimum-energy problems under bounded (admissible) controls. A. A. Azamov [15] focused on the application of Pontryagin's maximum principle to linear and differential control systems as well as pursuit-evasion games [14]. In the field of optimal control theory, Sh. A. Alimov and G. I. Ibragimov [20] determined control functions that minimize (or maximize) a given performance criterion under the dynamic constraints of the system [11], [19]. This approach makes it possible to identify the structural properties of optimal controls, in particular, bang-bang type controls and the role of switching functions.

In recent years, interest in optimal control theory has increased significantly, especially due to practical problems related to unmanned aerial vehicles and autonomous drones. Issues of coordinated motion of drones, as well as the optimal adjustment of their spatial orientation and positioning, have become highly important in logistics, aerial photography, search-and-rescue operations, and monitoring systems (Beard and McLain, 2012) [3]. In such applications, the boundedness of control signals, the nonlinearity of system dynamics, and the requirement to minimize time make the use of optimal control methods essential [2], [4].

The theory of pursuit-evasion type differential games with a prescribed duration and integral constraints on the controls was studied in depth by G. I. Ibragimov and A. Sh. Kuchkarov, who conducted research on optimal strategies and their applications

[10]. In contemporary studies, optimal trajectory planning problems for UAV systems are investigated based on various criteria. In particular, trajectories based on minimum energy or smoothness criteria (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011) [13], as well as optimal control models relying on the differential flatness properties of drone dynamics (Faessler et al., 2018) [7], have been extensively analyzed. However, in many real systems, control signals are strictly bounded [12], which gives rise to the need for a thorough theoretical investigation of minimum-time bang-bang controls.

From this perspective, the optimal motion of mechanical systems with a rigid geometric structure attracts particular scientific interest. Such models are effective for describing a system of rigidly connected drones or the planar translational and rotational motion of a single rigid platform [9], [18]. Determining the minimum-time optimal trajectories of these systems under bounded controls is theoretically challenging and requires an in-depth analysis based on Pontryagin's maximum principle (Agrachev and Sachkov, 2004) [1].

This paper investigates the minimum-time optimal control problem for a segment of constant length moving in the plane. The problem is analyzed using Pontryagin's maximum principle, demonstrating that the optimal controls have a bang-bang structure and providing a precise geometric interpretation of the optimal trajectory. The results contribute to the development of optimal control theory and have practical significance for motion planning problems of coordinated drones and robotic systems.

2. Problem statement and its reduction to an optimal control formulation

A segment AB of length $l > 0$ is given in the plane, with its initial position at the points

$$A = (a, b), \quad B = (a + l, b),$$

and its final position at the points

$$C = (0, 0), \quad D = (l, 0).$$

During the motion of the segment, its length remains constant, and the velocity vectors of its endpoints $A(t)$ and $B(t)$ are always perpendicular to the segment \overline{AB} and their magnitudes do not exceed 1.

2.1. Mathematical model

Let us denote $A(t) = (x_1(t), x_2(t))$, where $x_1(0) = a$, $x_2(0) = b$.

We introduce the state vector $x(t) = (x_1(t), x_2(t), \theta(t))$, where $\theta(t)$ is the angle formed by the segment $A(t)B(t)$ with the Ox axis.

Since the segment is rigid, the position of its second endpoint $B(t)$ is determined by

$$B(t) = (x_1(t) + l \cos \theta(t), x_2(t) + l \sin \theta(t)) = A(t) + l(\cos \theta(t), \sin \theta(t)) \quad (1)$$

It follows that

$$\overrightarrow{A(t)B(t)} = l(\cos \theta(t), \sin \theta(t)),$$

and the unit vector perpendicular to it has the form

$$(-\sin \theta(t), \cos \theta(t)).$$

Consequently, the velocity vectors of the segment's endpoints can be written as

$$\dot{A}(t) = u_1(t)(-\sin \theta(t), \cos \theta(t)), \quad \dot{B}(t) = u_2(t)(-\sin \theta(t), \cos \theta(t)), \quad (2)$$

where the control functions satisfy the constraints

$$|u_1(t)| \leq 1, \quad |u_2(t)| \leq 1.$$

Differentiating equation (1) with respect to time, we obtain

$$\dot{B}(t) = \dot{A}(t) + l(-\sin \theta(t) \cdot \dot{\theta}(t), \cos \theta(t) \cdot \dot{\theta}(t)) \quad (3)$$

From equations (2) and (3), it follows that

$$\dot{\theta}(t) = \frac{u_2(t) - u_1(t)}{l}.$$

As a result, the system is described by the following controlled dynamical system:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= -u_1 \sin \theta, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= u_1 \cos \theta, \\ \dot{\theta} &= \frac{u_2 - u_1}{l}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with the initial conditions

$$x_1(0) = a, \quad x_2(0) = b, \quad \theta(0) = 0.$$

The control set is defined as

$$U = (u_1, u_2) \in [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1].$$

The terminal state of the system is specified by the following set:

$$S = \left\{ (x_1, x_2, \theta) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \times [0, 2\pi) \mid x_1 = 0, x_2 = 0, \theta = 0 \right\}.$$

That is, for the optimal trajectory, the condition $x(T) \in S$ must be satisfied.

2.2. Optimal control problem

Based on the dynamic model presented above, we consider the minimum-time optimal control problem.

Problem (P). The control functions

$$u(\cdot) = (u_1(\cdot), u_2(\cdot)) \in U = [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$$

must be chosen so as to minimize the motion time T , while the state trajectory

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u) = \begin{bmatrix} -u_1 \sin \theta \\ u_1 \cos \theta \\ \frac{1}{l}(u_2 - u_1) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

satisfies the following initial and terminal conditions:

$$x(0) = (a, b, 0), \quad x(T) = (0, 0, 0).$$

Remark: Since the point $B(t)$ is expressed via $A(t)$ as

$$B(t) = A(t) + l(\cos \theta(t), \sin \theta(t)),$$

no separate state equation for $B(t)$ is included in the system dynamics.

The initial and terminal orientation conditions $\theta(0) = \theta(T) = 0$ and equation (4) imply the following integral constraint:

$$\int_0^T (u_2(t) - u_1(t)) dt = 0.$$

This condition ensures that the final orientation of the segment coincides with the initial one, i.e., the total rotation of the segment is zero.

2.3. Pontryagin's maximum principle

We consider the following control system:

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u), \quad u(t) \in U, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad x(T) = x_1.$$

For this system, the minimum-time optimal control problem is analyzed using Pontryagin's maximum principle (PMP).

If $u^*(\cdot)$ is an optimal control and $x^*(\cdot)$ is the corresponding optimal trajectory, then there exists a nonzero absolutely continuous adjoint vector function

$$p(\cdot) = (p_1(\cdot), p_2(\cdot), p_3(\cdot))$$

and a number $p_0 \leq 0$, which for the time-optimal problem is $p_0 = -1$. Furthermore, the condition

$$(p(\cdot), p_0) \neq 0$$

must be satisfied.

The Hamiltonian function is defined as

$$H(x, p, u) = p \cdot f(x, u) + p_0,$$

and the following necessary conditions must hold:

1) Hamiltonian system:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p}_1 &= -\frac{\partial H(x^*(t), p, u^*(t))}{\partial x_1}, \\ \dot{p}_2 &= -\frac{\partial H(x^*(t), p, u^*(t))}{\partial x_2}, \\ \dot{p}_3 &= -\frac{\partial H(x^*(t), p, u^*(t))}{\partial \theta}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

2) Maximum condition:

$$H(x^*(t), p(t), u^*(t)) = \max_{u \in U} H(x^*(t), p(t), u), \quad t \in [0, T]. \tag{7}$$

3) For the time-optimal control problem, along the optimal process,

$$H(x^*(t), p(t), u^*(t)) \equiv 0 \tag{8}$$

holds.

(4) For the system, the Hamiltonian function can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} H &= p \cdot f(x, u) - 1 \\ &= p_1(-u_1 \sin \theta) + p_2(u_1 \cos \theta) + p_3 \frac{u_2 - u_1}{l} - 1 \\ &= u_1 \left(-p_1 \sin \theta + p_2 \cos \theta - \frac{p_3}{l} \right) + u_2 \frac{p_3}{l} - 1 \\ &= u_1 \varphi_1(t) + u_2 \varphi_2(t) - 1, \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where

$$\varphi_1(t) = -p_1 \sin \theta + p_2 \cos \theta - \frac{p_3}{l}, \quad \varphi_2(t) = \frac{p_3}{l}$$

are the switching functions.

From the maximum condition, the Hamiltonian reaches its maximum under the following controls:

$$u_1(t) = \text{sign } \varphi_1(t), \quad u_2(t) = \text{sign } \varphi_2(t),$$

and if $\varphi_i(t) = 0$, then $u_i(t) \in [-1, 1]$ can be chosen arbitrarily. Therefore,

$$u_1 \in \{-1, 1\}, \quad u_2 \in \{-1, 1\},$$

i.e., the optimal control is of the bang-bang type [8].

From the Hamiltonian system, the adjoint equations take the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p}_1 &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial x_1} = 0, \\ \dot{p}_2 &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial x_2} = 0, \\ \dot{p}_3 &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial \theta} = u_1(p_1 \cos \theta + p_2 \sin \theta). \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

We introduce the following notations:

$$\begin{aligned} q &= p_1 \cos \theta + p_2 \sin \theta, \\ r &= -p_1 \sin \theta + p_2 \cos \theta. \end{aligned}$$

Using these notations, the switching functions take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1 &= r - \frac{p_3}{l}, \\ \varphi_2 &= \frac{p_3}{l}, \\ \dot{p}_3 &= u_1 q. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, the optimal control is determined as follows:

$$u_1(t) = \begin{cases} +1, & \varphi_1(t) > 0, \\ -1, & \varphi_1(t) < 0, \end{cases} \quad u_2(t) = \begin{cases} +1, & \varphi_2(t) > 0, \\ -1, & \varphi_2(t) < 0. \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

From the third necessary condition for the Hamiltonian, i.e., $H \equiv 0$, it follows that

$$u_1(t)\varphi_1(t) + u_2(t)\varphi_2(t) = 1.$$

3. Solving the optimal control problem

The point $M(t)$, defined as the geometric midpoint of the segment $A(t)B(t)$, plays an important role in describing the overall motion of the system. Its coordinates are given by

$$M = \left(x_1 + \frac{l}{2} \cos \theta, x_2 + \frac{l}{2} \sin \theta \right).$$

This expression clearly shows that the position of the point M depends on the coordinates x_1, x_2 and the orientation angle θ of the body.

The velocity vector of the point M is obtained by differentiating with respect to time:

$$\dot{M} = \left(\dot{x}_1 - \frac{l}{2} \sin \theta \cdot \dot{\theta}, \dot{x}_2 + \frac{l}{2} \cos \theta \cdot \dot{\theta} \right).$$

Here, the first term represents the translational motion, while the second term accounts for the contribution of rotational motion to the midpoint.

Taking into account the state equations of the control system, the velocity of the point M can be simplified to

$$\dot{M} = \frac{u_1 + u_2}{2} (-\sin \theta, \cos \theta) = s(-\sin \theta, \cos \theta),$$

where

$$s = \frac{u_1 + u_2}{2}. \quad (12)$$

Thus, the point M moves at each instant in a direction perpendicular to the angle θ . The magnitude s represents the translational speed of M and equals the average of the two controls.

The modulus of the velocity vector is

$$|\dot{M}| = |s|,$$

i.e., the speed of the point M is determined solely by the parameter s .

To separate the relative influence of the controls, we introduce the following notation:

$$a = \frac{u_2 - u_1}{2}, \quad \dot{\theta} = \frac{2a}{l}. \quad (13)$$

Here, the magnitude a represents the angular velocity of the system and is determined by the difference of the controls. Thus, if u_1 and u_2 are equal, the system moves straight without rotation; otherwise, a rotational motion occurs.

Consequently, instead of the original controls (u_1, u_2) , the motion of the system can be described by the pair (s, a) , which simplifies the model both geometrically and analytically.

Using the constraints $|u_1| \leq 1, |u_2| \leq 1$ and $u_1 = \pm k \cdot u_2, 0 \leq k \leq 1$, the following important estimate is obtained:

$$|s| + |a| \leq 1. \quad (14)$$

This inequality describes the admissible region in the control space as a rhombus and indicates that the optimal control has bang-bang character.

3.1. Reduction of the Problem to its Equivalent Form

Using the notations introduced in the previous section, the problem can be represented in an equivalent geometric form. That is, the initial and final positions of the point M are given by

$$M(0) = M_0 = \left(a + \frac{l}{2}, b \right), \quad M(T) = M_1 = \left(\frac{l}{2}, 0 \right).$$

Moreover, the orientation of the system at the initial and final times is required to be the same, i.e.,

$$\theta(0) = \theta(T) = 0.$$

Among the trajectories satisfying these conditions, the goal is to find the one minimizing the final time T [5]. For simplicity, we assume

$$a < 0, \quad b < 0,$$

i.e., the point M_0 is located in the third quadrant of the coordinate plane.

According to the maximum condition obtained in the previous section, the optimal controls in equation (11) take one of the following four combinations:

$$\begin{aligned} 1) & \quad u_1 = 1, \quad u_2 = 1, \\ 2) & \quad u_1 = 1, \quad u_2 = -1, \\ 3) & \quad u_1 = -1, \quad u_2 = 1, \\ 4) & \quad u_1 = -1, \quad u_2 = -1. \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

We now analyze each of these cases separately.

Case 1. If

$$u_1 = u_2 = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad u_1 = u_2 = -1,$$

then, from the definitions

$$s = \frac{u_1 + u_2}{2}, \quad a = \frac{u_2 - u_1}{2}$$

introduced in the previous section, we have

$$a = 0, \quad s = \pm 1.$$

Hence,

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{2a}{l} = 0,$$

i.e., the orientation of the system does not change. In this case, the motion consists purely of a parallel translation, and the trajectory is a straight line.

Case 2. If

$$(u_1, u_2) = (1, -1) \quad \text{or} \quad (u_1, u_2) = (-1, 1),$$

i.e., u_1 and u_2 have opposite signs, then

$$s = 0, \quad a = \pm 1.$$

This means that there is no parallel translation, and the motion consists solely of rotation.

The length of the segment connecting the initial and final points is

$$|M_0M_1| = |AC| = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}.$$

For the direction of rotation to align with the segment M_0M_1 , the motion direction vector $(-\sin \theta, \cos \theta)$ must be parallel to this segment, i.e.,

$$(-\sin \theta, \cos \theta) \parallel M_0M_1.$$

From this condition, the rotation angle $\theta = \theta^*$ is determined as

$$\sin \theta^* = \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}, \quad \cos \theta^* = -\frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}.$$

Taking into account that $a < 0$ and $b < 0$, we see that

$$\theta^* \in \left(-\frac{\pi}{2}, 0\right).$$

3.2. Transferring segment AB to segment CD in minimum Time

Based on the results obtained in the previous sections, we constructively solve the problem of transferring the segment AB from the given initial position to the position of segment CD in minimum time.

From a geometric point of view, the optimal trajectory can consist of three sequential elementary motions:

1. Rotate the segment AB to the angle θ^* ;
2. Translate the resulting segment $A(\theta^*)B(\theta^*)$ parallel to the vector $\overrightarrow{M_0M_1}$;
3. Rotate the segment back from θ^* to reach the final orientation.

We now estimate the time required for these motions.

Time required for parallel translation. Since the speed of the point M is $|s|$, in order to cover the distance $R = |M_0M_1|$ from M_0 to M_1 , it is necessary that

$$\int_0^T |s(t)| dt \geq R.$$

Time required for rotation. Since the rotational speed is $\dot{\theta} = \frac{2a}{l}$, the total rotation can be estimated as

$$\int_0^T |\dot{\theta}(t)| dt.$$

As the segment must first rotate from 0 to θ^* and then back from θ^* to 0, the total rotation is $2|\theta^*|$. Therefore,

$$\int_0^T |a(t)| dt \geq \frac{l}{2} \int_0^T |\dot{\theta}(t)| dt \geq \frac{l}{2} \cdot 2|\theta^*| = l|\theta^*|.$$

As indicated in the previous section, the controls satisfy

$$|s(t)| + |a(t)| \leq 1.$$

Hence,

$$T \geq \int_0^T (|s(t)| + |a(t)|) dt \geq R + l|\theta^*|,$$

i.e.,

$$T \geq R + l|\theta^*|$$

is a valid inequality.

We now show that it is indeed possible to transfer the segment AB to CD within the time $R + l|\theta^*|$, i.e., this bound is sharp (achievable).

Stage I: Rotation. Choose the controls as

$$u_1 = 1, \quad u_2 = -1.$$

Then

$$s = 0, \quad a = -1, \quad \dot{\theta} = -\frac{2}{l}.$$

Consequently, the segment rotates only, and the time required to rotate from 0 to $\theta^* < 0$ is

$$T_1 = \frac{l}{2}|\theta^*|.$$

Stage II: Parallel translation. Now choose the controls as

$$u_1 = 1, \quad u_2 = 1.$$

In this case,

$$s = 1, \quad a = 0,$$

i.e., there is no rotation, only parallel translation. The velocity vector of the point M is

$$\dot{M} = (-\sin \theta^*, \cos \theta^*) = \left(-\frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}, -\frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right),$$

which is aligned with the direction of M_0M_1 . Thus, the point M traverses the segment M_0M_1 with unit speed, requiring

$$T_2 = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} = R$$

time.

Stage III: Reverse rotation. In the final stage, the controls are chosen as

$$u_1 = -1, \quad u_2 = 1.$$

Then

$$s = 0, \quad a = 1, \quad \dot{\theta} = \frac{2}{l}.$$

The segment rotates back from θ^* to 0. The time required for this process is

$$T_3 = \frac{l}{2}|\theta^*|.$$

Thus, the total time is

$$T = T_1 + T_2 + T_3 = R + l|\theta^*| \quad (16)$$

which coincides with the lower bound obtained above. Hence, expression (16) provides the optimal solution of the problem, i.e., the minimal achievable time.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, the time-optimal control problem for a mechanical segment with fixed length moving in a plane was analyzed using Pontryagin's maximum principle. Based on the system dynamics and imposed constraints, it was shown that the optimal controls have a bang-bang structure, and the geometric interpretation of the optimal trajectory was determined through the properties of the switching functions. The theoretical results obtained serve as a methodological basis for designing effective control strategies for rigidly connected objects and coordinated motion of drones. Furthermore, the findings expand the applicability of optimal control theory in practical areas and suggest the study of tightly constrained control problems described by higher-order differential equations in future research.

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